

Prevalence and Severity of Dental Fluorosis Among School Children In Deobhog Block, Chhattisgarh : A Comparative Cross-Sectional Study

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Abstract

Background : Fluorosis remains a public health concern in several Indian states due to excessive fluoride in groundwater. Dental fluorosis, particularly among children, is an early indicator of chronic fluoride exposure. Deobhog block in Gariaband district, Chhattisgarh, has been identified as a fluoride-affected region, though limited systematic data exists on its prevalence and severity among children.

Aim : To assess and compare the prevalence and severity of dental fluorosis among primary (6-9 years) and middle school (10-13 years) children in Deobhog block and correlate these findings with village-level groundwater fluoride concentrations.

Materials and Methods : A comparative cross-sectional study was conducted among 2,928 schoolchildren from 56 schools across 33 villages. Participants were categorized into two age-based groups: Group 1 (6–9 years; n = 1,464) and Group 2 (10–13 years; n = 1,464). Dental fluorosis was assessed using Dean's Fluorosis Index under natural daylight by trained dental professionals. Groundwater fluoride levels were obtained from the Central Ground Water Board's 2023 report.

Results : The prevalence of dental fluorosis was higher among middle school children (63.7%) compared to primary school children (54.0%). Moderate to severe fluorosis was observed in 8.3% of middle school children and 5.4% of primary school children. A significant correlation was found between age, severity of fluorosis, and village-level fluoride concentration ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion : The study highlights a substantial burden of dental fluorosis among children in Deobhog block, with increasing severity observed in older age groups. These findings underscore the need for regular screening, community awareness, and implementation of safe water practices to prevent further progression of fluorosis in affected regions.

Keywords - Fluorosis, Groundwater, School children, Dean's Index

INTRODUCTION

Fluorosis is a pressing public health concern in various regions of India, especially in areas where drinking water contains high levels of naturally occurring fluoride¹. While fluoride plays a critical role in preventing dental caries at optimal concentrations² (approximately 0.7–1.2 ppm), chronic exposure to elevated levels during early childhood can lead to dental fluorosis, a condition characterized by hypo-mineralization of tooth enamel³. In severe cases, skeletal fluorosis may also develop, resulting in serious bone and joint deformities⁴.

India is among the most severely affected countries globally, with more than 20 states reporting fluoride contamination in groundwater⁵. Emerging evidence points to central and eastern regions, including Chhattisgarh, as being increasingly impacted. Deobhog block in Gariaband district has been identified by local health authorities as an endemic fluorosis zone, based on field reports

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and complaints from communities, particularly concerning dental discoloration in children. However, systematic studies documenting the burden and severity of fluorosis in this region, particularly among school-aged children, are limited.

Children aged 6-13 years are particularly susceptible to the effects of fluoride, as their permanent teeth are still developing⁶. Dental fluorosis in this population serves not only as a clinical marker of excessive fluoride intake but also as a social concern due to the impact on facial aesthetics and self-esteem⁷.

Early identification and monitoring of dental fluorosis in schoolchildren are essential to mitigate long-term health effects. Schools offer a practical and efficient setting for mass screening and potential implementation of oral health interventions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A comparative cross-sectional study was conducted in Deobhog block, Gariaband district, Chhattisgarh - A region officially classified as fluoride-affected by the Central Ground Water Board (CGWB). The study aimed to determine and compare the prevalence and severity of dental fluorosis in primary (6-9 years) and middle school children (10-13 years).

Study Population

A total of 2961 school children were examined across 56 schools in 33 villages, A census method was adopted. All students present during the school visits and meeting the inclusion criteria were screened.

Inclusion Criteria

- Children within 6 to 13 years age were selected
- Enrollment in government or private schools in Deobhog block
- Resident of the respective village
- Present during the school visit

Exclusion Criteria

- Recent migrant students
- Children with non-fluorotic enamel defects (e.g., enamel hypoplasia)
- Children with developmental or systemic conditions affecting enamel

Participants were divided into two age-based groups (Flow chart 1)

Group 1: Primary school (6-9 years)

Group 2: Middle school (10-13 years)

Flow Chart 1 - Subject Distribution

These groups were compared in terms of:

- Prevalence and severity of dental fluorosis (using Dean's Index)
- Village-level fluoride exposure

Oral examinations were carried out by a trained dental team using Dean's Fluorosis Index under natural daylight, with sterile mouth mirrors and probes (Fig 1).

Fig 1 - Diagnosing fluorosis index

Findings were recorded on structured proformas (Fig 2). Each school was visited once according to a predetermined schedule.

Fig 2 - Recording the Findings

Groundwater fluoride levels for each village were obtained from the CGWB's 2023 report. Villages were stratified into three categories based on fluoride concentration:

- 1.5-3.0 ppm
- 3.0-5.0 ppm
- 5.0 ppm

These categories were used to correlate village water fluoride levels with the prevalence and severity of dental fluorosis.

Ethical Considerations

- Permission was obtained from the District Education Office and Block Health Department.
- Verbal consent was taken from school authorities.
- Only non-invasive examinations were conducted.

- Identified cases were referred for further management or counselling.

RESULTS

Data were compiled in Microsoft Excel and analysed using SPSS v25 and R software. Descriptive statistics (n, %, mean prevalence). In the primary school group, 46.0% of children showed no signs of fluorosis, whereas in the middle school group, only 36.3% were fluorosis-free. The prevalence of moderate to severe fluorosis (grades of clinical concern) increased from 5.4% in primary children to 8.3% in middle school children. Mild and very mild fluorosis were also more frequently observed in the older age group. (Table 1)

Dean's Fluorosis Score	Primary School (n = 1464)	Middle School (n = 1464)
Normal	674 (46.0%)	532 (36.3%)
Questionable	342 (23.4%)	302 (20.6%)
Very Mild	145 (9.9%)	218 (14.9%)
Mild	223 (15.2%)	325 (22.2%)
Moderate	68 (4.6%)	105 (7.2%)
Severe	12 (0.8%)	16 (1.1%)

Table 1 - Distribution of Dental Fluorosis According to Dean's Fluorosis Index

Overall prevalence of dental fluorosis was found to be significant across both age groups. The middle school group (10–13 years) showed a higher prevalence and greater severity of fluorosis compared to the primary school group (6–9 years).

Graph 1 - Distribution of Dental Fluorosis Among School Children in Deobhog Block

A positive correlation was observed between fluoride levels in drinking water and both the prevalence and severity of dental fluorosis. Villages with >5.0 ppm fluoride levels had the highest number of children with moderate to severe forms of fluorosis based on Dean's Index. The Chi-square test indicated a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) in fluorosis prevalence between the two age groups. Spearman's correlation confirmed a strong association ($r > 0.6$, $p < 0.05$) between water fluoride content and fluorosis prevalence. (Graph 1)

DISCUSSION

This study reveals a substantial burden of dental fluorosis among schoolchildren in the Deobhog block of Chhattisgarh, a region increasingly recognized for endemic fluoride exposure. The significantly higher prevalence and severity of fluorosis in middle school children (10–13 years) compared to primary school children (6–9 years) suggests a pattern of cumulative fluoride exposure over time. This is consistent with the established pathophysiology of dental fluorosis, which primarily affects developing teeth during enamel mineralization. Dean (1947) was one of the earliest to establish this developmental relationship, showing that the duration and concentration of fluoride exposure are critical in determining the severity of fluorosis⁸.

Our study further confirmed a positive correlation between village-level groundwater fluoride concentrations and the severity of fluorosis among children. Villages with fluoride levels ≥ 5 ppm reported notably more moderate to severe cases, in line with findings from other parts of India. For example, J Hussain, KC Sharma et al. (2004) reported that regions in Rajasthan with high fluoride levels had similarly elevated rates of dental and skeletal fluorosis⁹. Likewise, N Arveti, MRS Sarma, et al. (2011) documented a direct relationship between fluoride levels and clinical severity of fluorosis in the populations of Andhra Pradesh¹⁰.

The findings of the present study highlight the urgent need for community-level public health interventions. Essential measures include routine monitoring of fluoride levels in drinking water, the provision of defluoridated or alternative safe water sources, and mass awareness campaigns to educate communities about the health risks of excess fluoride. These interventions are supported by WHO guidelines (2004), which emphasize the importance of maintaining fluoride concentrations in drinking water below 1.5 ppm to avoid adverse health effects¹¹.

Moreover, the success of this school-based survey underscores the utility of educational institutions as effective platforms for early detection and monitoring of dental health issues in vulnerable populations. Similar strategies were recommended by Ayoob and Gupta (2006), who advocated for school-based oral health programs as efficient tools for both surveillance and preventive education¹².

In terms of public health implications, although most children in this study had mild to very mild forms of fluorosis, the proportion of moderate to severe cases—particularly among older children—is clinically important. These forms can have aesthetic, psychological, and functional consequences, potentially affecting a child's self-esteem and quality of life. H.Siddiq, KC Pentapati, et al. (2020) pointed out that children with visible dental fluorosis often face social stigma, further justifying the need for timely intervention¹³.

In conclusion, our study reinforces the need for early identification, age-targeted educational interventions, and systemic public health responses to combat fluorosis in affected regions.

Implementing routine school-based oral screening, coupled with broader fluoride mitigation strategies, can play a pivotal role in reducing the long-term impact of fluorosis in children exposed to high-risk environments like Deobhog.

CONCLUSION

The Deobhog block exhibits a high burden of dental fluorosis among schoolchildren, with a clear link to elevated groundwater fluoride levels. The results highlight the need for urgent public health interventions aimed at mitigating fluoride exposure and managing its oral health consequences in affected communities.

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